

GreenFORCE

Foster Research Excellence for Green Transition in the Western Balkans

Deliverable 2.4 – 1st group of policy briefs formulated for the steering of green transitions in the WB – 2 briefs

Grant no: 101059411
Type of action: HORIZON Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Project start date 01/07/2022
Project end date 30/06/2025
Cordis link <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101059411>

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Deliverable Information:

Deliverable leader	Nordregio
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Contractual delivery date	30/09/2023
Delivery date	30/09/2023
Resubmitted	31/10/2023
Dissemination level	PU

Version History:

Version	Date	Main author/s	Summary of changes
V.0	05/08/2023	Fiona Imami, Anila Bejko	Policy Brief no 1, first draft shared for comments with Nordregio
Vo.1	15/09/2023	Alberto Giacometti, Carlos Tapia	First draft document shared for comments with all partners
Vo.2	12/07/2023	Merita Toska, Rodion Gjoka	Policy Brief no 2, first draft/ structure shared for comments with Nordregio
Vo.3	26/09/2023	Alberto Giacometti	Policy Brief no 2, shared with all partners for comments
Vo.4	22/09/2023	All partners	Revised document - comments from all partners on Policy Brief no 1
Vo.5	29/09/2023	Alberto Giacometti	Finalising Draft Document, still some pending comments to be addressed
Vo.3	30/09/2023	Alberto Giacometti, Anila Bejko, Fiona Imami	Finalised for submission as draft deliverable
Vo.4	25/10/2023	Alberto Giacometti, Anila Bejko, Rodion Gjoka, Merita Toska	Finalized document for re-submission

Quality Review:

Activity	Name	Date
Prepared	Co-PLAN and Nordregio	15/09/2023
Reviewed	All partners	22/09/2023
Revised	Nordregio and Co-PLAN	30/09/2023
Finalised	Nordregio and Co-PLAN	25/10/2023

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List of Abbreviations

EGD: European Green Deal

GAWB: Green Agenda for the Western Balkans

JGT: Just Green Transition

RDF: Refuse-Derived Fuel

SRF: Solid Recovered Fuel

WB: Western Balkans

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable (D2.4) consists of a first set of policy briefs (x2) out of a total of five policy briefs that are to be developed within Wp2 – Task 2.4 of the GreenFORCE, Horizon Europe project. The project aims at fostering excellence in the "Western Balkans' green transition" and scientific research capacities of Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (Albania), Center for Economic Analysis (North Macedonia), and University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography (Serbia), by working together in twinning with Nordregio - Nordic Institute for Regional Development and Planning - (Sweden) and Politecnico di Torino (Italy). The collaboration is working to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning.

Developing policy relevant documents based on research results is one key focus of this consortium towards increasing capacities of WB organisations, particularly in reaching out to policy makers with evidence-based information about the most pressing issues surrounding the Just Green Transition (JGT). The first step of the process consisted on a hybrid training session (in Skopje and online) led by Nordregio with the support of POLITO on how to develop content of policymaking use focusing on the experiences of researchers in these two organisations in developing policy briefs, policy recommendations, and other types of policy documents based on outputs from the research (e.g. reports, academic articles). A second training session was organised in Tirana with the research staff of Co-PLAN.

The second step, consisted on applying the learnings in the development of policy briefs relevant to green transition in WB, by WB organisations taking lead as authors with close support of Nordregio as editor, with contribution of all partners. This approach was of key importance to ensure a bottom-up process where the issues presented, deemed of policy relevance, as well as the recommendations, emerge from experts in the region and not from alien organisations. At the same time, editors and POLITO played a supporting role in relation to form (style, language, format, etc) and as scientific quality assuring (scientific backing, contextualisation, etc).

2. Summary of the Policy Briefs

2.1 1st Policy Brief: “Just Green Transition in the Western Balkans: Overcoming Transitions Fatigue”

This policy brief and recommendations build on the “Report on Western Balkans Just Green Transition Conceptualisation”, in addition to contributions of researchers from the GreenFORCE consortium partnership. It combines a conceptual basis of the JGT [a process entailing far-reaching technological, institutional, and behavioural changes (transition) that should contribute to reducing the impacts of the environmental crisis (green) and shall take place in a socially-fair way (just)], with a critical view of top-down – alien – policy frameworks that aim (and have aimed) at engineering profound ‘transitions’ to the political, social, economic and technological systems in the Western Balkans. The policy brief argues that to ensure the success of the JGT in the WB countries will depend on their own ability to, first, truly comprehend our socio-economic contexts, and second, to design their own roadmap based on a realistic, bottom-up, and self-defined action points. Policy recommendations provide some hints to how to achieve this.

See the full policy brief document in Annex 1

2.2 2nd Policy Brief: “Waste to Energy: Unlocking the Potential of Waste as an Alternative Source of Energy in the Western Balkans”

This policy brief and recommendations build previous research conducted by Co-PLAN on Waste to Energy in the Cement Industry for the Western Balkans. It highlights both the huge problems WB countries have in connection to their waste management systems, both to the environment and to human health, and the important opportunities (political, economic, social, environmental) of making a better use of wasted resources. While vast quantities of waste lie dormant in landfills, awaiting decomposition over centuries or incineration, a substantial portion of these waste streams conceals untapped potential in the production of energy and other materials. Harnessing the latent potential residing within waste materials represents a huge opportunity for achieving the ambitious sustainability targets and improving human health and generating economic opportunities. Among other things, this brief proposes to shift focus from a disposal-oriented (linear) to a value-creation approach (circular). By changing the understanding of ‘waste’ to ‘resource’ can help prolonging the life of resources, thus reducing the environmental footprint, while generating additional revenues, which can be an incentive for private investors to offer new ways of managing waste, or else can be used to increase capacities within the public administration and improve the quality of services. Policy recommendations offer some hints on how to unlock the potential of waste in the WB.

See the full policy brief document in Annex 2

Annexes

Annex 1: Policy Brief: “Just Green Transition in the Western Balkans: Overcoming Transitions Fatigue”

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JUST GREEN TRANSITION IN THE WESTERN BALKANS OVERCOMING TRANSITIONS FATIGUE

“Just Green Transition” (JGT) is the term used today to describe the global crusade to transit from unsustainable economic models towards a carbon neutral economy. This process entails far-reaching technological, institutional, and behavioural changes (transition) that should contribute to reducing the impacts of the environmental crisis (green) and shall take place in a socially-fair way (just).

In the Western Balkans (WB), however, the JGT is, so far, mostly used as a buzzword without fully generating the necessary awareness of the scale and transformative nature it implies. This is reflected

in the absence of a comprehensive approach to coordinating climate and environmental action. Instead, there is a patchwork of policy initiatives tackling specific sectors. Furthermore, as the WB countries commit to the JGT, a key concern is how to land the narrative of a ‘transition’ in a region that has been subject to several transitions through history with questionable levels of success.

This policy brief aims to increase clarity of what are the practical implications of JGT for the WB region and for its domestic policy arena, and offer recommendations for how to achieve better policy implementation and increased societal support.

What is Just Green Transition?

Policy background

The just transition concept is rooted in the struggles of the American unions during the 1970s and 1980s to protect jobs during processes of industrial reconversion. The notion of a 'just transition' was formalised and mainstreamed into the climate agenda in the 1990s, with similar aims, namely to protect workers whose jobs were at risk due to climate policies. Today, the notion of JGT expanded and refers to fair sustainability transitions where 'no person and no place are left behind'.

The notion of JGT gained political momentum after the approval of the Paris Agreement and today it is an integral part of the European Green Deal (EGD), the union's new growth strategy. The EGD aims to transform the union into a modern, resource-efficient, and competitive economy while reaching climate neutrality, reducing waste and pollution, moving to a circular and resource-efficient economy, and stopping the loss of biodiversity. In addition, the strategy establishes implementation mechanisms for ensuring a "just transition". The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans (GAWB) represents an extension of the EGD.

Beyond policy

The JGT combines three concepts, each with its own independent theoretical and practical traditions; 1) **transitions**, 2) **the green economy**, and 3) **social justice**.

The JGT, is a type of socio-technical transition, which requires a shift from one sociotechnical regime (a carbon economy) to another (a sustainable economy). In practice, this means that the process of industrial transformation and implementation of technological innovations, such as renewable energies, electrification of vehicles, or precision agriculture, need to go hand-in-hand with changes in the institutional structures, and the overall organisation of society and economic activity. This is why, despite the access to knowledge and new technologies, they often take time to be adopted, as economic activity is embedded in social norms, practices, and the 'way-to-do-things' in different countries and regions. Conversely, place-specific conditions shape the way innovations are materialised.

Green socio-technical transitions are extremely complex and difficult to engineer, and often require painful trade-offs between economic, societal, and environmental objectives that may lead to a range of outcomes with winners and losers. An approach to justice is, therefore, the key to ensuring an inclusive and fair process, and to design effective measures to mitigate the negative consequences of a transition.

Transitions

Transition denotes a dynamic process of change from one state to another. Transitions theory has been extensively applied across disciplines such as economics, sociology, political science, environmental, and innovation studies.

'Socio-technical transitions' refer to systemic change across the complex interrelatedness of social, economic, institutional, and technological elements in the organisation of a system.

Green economy

Green economy is one that requires low levels of carbon. The term emerged from the realisation that human activity needs to be restricted to a 'safe zone', not to cross the 'planetary boundaries' or limits to which the earth systems are able to self-regulate and recover.

The transition to a green economy involves changes to all sectors, from energy and transport to construction, industry, agriculture, forestry, and all links to the production and consumption chains. This includes the application of new technologies, increased resource efficiency, as well as the move from a linear to a circular economy.

Social justice

A cry for 'just transitions' popularised in the 1970s and 1980s by trade unions in the US and Canada concerned about the consequences of environmental protection policies on jobs, and reflected the development of a justice-based political discourse in the 19th century, often linked to the distribution of income and wealth.

In the context of green transitions, the commonly referred forms of justice, are: i) 'distributional justice' pointing to where the impacts (costs and benefits) are located or distributed, ii) 'recognitional justice' referring to which societal groups are recognised or neglected in policy processes iii) 'Procedural justice': entailing the formal and informal forms of involvement in decision-making processes.

Additionally, spatial justice popularised in the 1970' linking social-justice to space/territory. It focuses both on redistributive issues thus the distribution of burdens and benefits across different geographical areas, and decision-making processes.

Western Balkans in between transitions

The JGT, both as a concept and as a policy framework, is being introduced in the Balkans via the GAWB. Formalised in 2020 with the Sofia Declaration, the GAWB is the basis for a new growth strategy for the region, embedded in the EU Economic and Investment Plan for the Western Balkans. This entails the adoption of EU directives and transposition of regulation across policy areas and on a wide range of issues, from climate law, meeting energy efficiency goals,

air and water quality standards, to the waste management framework, limiting pollution, increasing circularity, etc. This first step needs to be followed by implementation, leading to 'real', tangible change in all industrial sectors. This, we argue, represents an effort of colossal dimensions, matching or even surpassing the scale of transformations experienced in the region, first, in the post-communist transition, and second, as conditionality to EU accession.

The terminology used here resonates with past and ongoing transformations. The term 'transition', in fact, was exhaustively employed in the post-communist era in the early 1990's, specifically to label Central and Eastern European countries as 'transition countries'. A 'purposive transition' was set in motion characterised by a deliberate goal of transformation with an explicit set of societal expectations and drawing heavily on foreign aid and political steering. This transition was signalling epochal change and at the same time involving great degree of uncertainty. With time WB countries embarked on varying hybrid political-economic models, regardless of the path designated by the Western agents centred on privatisation, liberalisation, and democratisation.

While still transiting towards fully functional liberal democratic systems, in the early 2000's, WB countries were offered a trajectory for integration into the European Union, again consisting of a prescribed list of structural and political reforms. However, despite the financial and technical support provided, the integration process soon became a moving target. This is partly due to changing conditions, moving away from its original course towards an increased emphasis on tackling democratic shortfalls in the region, in addition to the rapidly changing

rules within the EU common market. These changes have had an overwhelming effect on the WB society at large and made the practical implementation an, arguably, impossible task.

All in all, the promises of a 'transition to' a liberal democracy, of a free economy, or a spot within the EU, have all generated high expectations in the past few decades, just for many to be disillusioned with the poor performance of the economic and social policies set in motion and the uncertain outlook. The path towards EU accession has been obstructed by the (arguably) unrealistic expectations, in combination with the incapability of the WB countries to set themselves afoot on a workable development path, as well as difficult governance of multilateralism at the interior of the EU, creating obstacles for further expansions. This situation, we argue, has produced a 'transitions fatigue' or a general sense of scepticism, or even mistrust, towards policies prescribed by external entities, as well as the ability of the political class in the WB to design comprehensive and place-sensitive policies.

In this context, unless serious efforts are made to transform the countries from within, the JGT, channelled via the GAWB, risks ending in the bucket of unaccomplished transitions,

Overcoming the transition fatigue

The future development path of the WBs, including the JGT, is in our own hands. A key impediment, we argue, is the prevailing expectation that foreign aid and eventually EU membership will solve structural problems in the region, from unemployment to public management. Neither will. These ungrounded expectations may be preventing us from building a sense of ownership of our own future and taking responsibility for laying the path forward.

Carrying on the JGT, therefore, will depend on the ability of WB countries to, first, truly comprehend our socio-economic contexts, and second, to design our own roadmap based on a realistic, bottom-up, and self-defined action points decoupling economic progress from environmental degradation. As follows, we propose a set of recommendations which should be addressed and coordinated at multiple levels (macro-regional, national and local).

Ensuring that no person and no place is left behind in the transition

- **Recognise (identify)** all potentially affected groups and map all types of impacts individual interventions may have to them, particularly the most vulnerable groups.
- **Ensure procedural justice, by creating opportunities for participation of all the identified stakeholders and affected groups.** Enable all stakeholders to bring to the discussion table their views, interests and priorities and enable a genuine process of dialogue aiming at building consensus. This will allow democratising decision-making processes, overcome challenges emerging from necessary trade-offs between different objectives, to build trust among stakeholders, and to create a sense of ownership of the green agenda. To achieve this, make use of existing networks and platforms for policy discussion and coordination, such as TG WeB, RCC, Nalas, WB Info Hub Platform, etc.
- **Make sure that costs/burdens and benefits are fairly distributed, among all societal groups, especially the most vulnerable.** This could be enabled, first, by recognizing all potentially affected vulnerable groups and further mapping impacts of individual interventions to different societal groups and territories, to properly design measures to mitigate the most affected.

In addition to ensure, spatial justice we should:

- **Design place-based strategies that are sensible to the specific spatial and territorial implications of transition measures.** In the spirit of a 'just transition' ensure that policies consider the local needs and interests.
- **Develop tailor-made action plans targeting developments with the highest impact potential.** Capitalise on successful industrial developments, community initiatives, or public management practices.
- **Explore business - models that give communities the option of participation or co-ownership of new business ventures to receive a share of the benefits.** For example, in wind and solar energy projects - allowing citizens to buy shares.

Build capacities and allocate resources for the technical transition

- **Build capacities within the public administration to gain better understanding of the practical and technical implication of policy measures towards transition.** Besides knowledge, empower the technical staff by giving them the tools and funding necessary for implementation.

- **Prioritise training and reskilling the workforce to adequately equip professionals with the knowledge and tools to adapt to the changing labour market needs.** Monitor closely the global trends and development of the technical frontier in critical sectors and ensure education programmes quickly adapt to emerging needs. Work at all levels, from formal education curricula, higher education, as well as professional re-education programmes (providing the opportunities for life-long-learning).
- **Create a common understanding of key concepts, targets, and the scope of interventions among all stakeholders.** Build consensus based on jointly created knowledge, sensible to Western Balkans specific context and aspirations.
- **Decrease the communication gap between key players** from different sectors by reinforcing cooperation and engagement by establishing genuine participatory processes on the path towards implementation of the green agenda.
- **Foster innovation processes at all levels.** This entails supporting research and innovation efforts related to the transitions, as well as institutional innovations within public administrations to enable private initiatives to develop.

Managing expectations with better communication

- **Foster transparency and inclusiveness in communicating green transition policies and agenda.** This entails providing clear, reliable, and honest information regarding the objectives, processes, and expected outcomes of these policies while addressing concerns proactively and openly discussing with all relevant stakeholders.
- **Generate clear understanding of what the practical implication of JGT entails for different government tiers and policy sectors.** Highlight the challenges and opportunities it poses for different sectors and territories offering fact-based and reliable information based on research and up to date studies.
- **Develop communication tools** for effective communication by the administrative staff, to help navigate through misleading information about the green transition.
- **Keep focus on the bigger picture** to be able to navigate around the complex landscape of socio-technical transformations. This means to be able to zoom-in and out from partial or immediate milestones (e.g., share of renewable energy targets), to the overall objectives (e.g., battling climate change, and fair transitions). This will help making better decisions where objectives are in conflict with each other.
- **Recognize the inter - connectedness between various technological and industrial regimes,** and to make informed and sensible decisions considering the, often painful, trade-offs that need to be made during these transformations.
- **Work incrementally by supporting ongoing promising developments** (even if embryonic) and endogenous potentials (low hanging fruits) and build from there onto more complex problems. Furthermore, identify the opportunities that can spin-off from ongoing developments. A thorough mapping of promising initiatives, local strengths and forward-looking actors is an important first step.

Adopting a systems perspective

ABOUT THIS POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief was developed by GreenFORCE, a Horizon Europe project which aims at fostering excellence in the “Western Balkans’ green transition” and scientific research capacities of Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (Albania), Center for Economic Analysis (North Macedonia), and University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography (Serbia). These organisations in twinship with Nordregio - Nordic Institute for Regional Development and Planning - (Sweden) and Politecnico di Torino (Italy) are working closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning.

The policy brief and recommendations build on the Report on “Western Balkans Just Green Transition Conceptualisation”, available in the GreenFORCE project website (<https://greenforcetwinning.net>) in addition to contributions of researchers from the GreenFORCE consortium partnership.

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Photos:

Photos from GreenFORCE project archive

Key references

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Annexes

Annex 2: Policy Brief: “Waste to Energy: Unlocking the Potential of Waste as an Alternative Source of Energy in the Western Balkans”

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WASTE TO ENERGY

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF WASTE AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOURCE OF ENERGY IN THE WESTERN BALKANS

Throughout the Western Balkans, waste is still considered an externality since vast quantities of waste are being deposited in open dump sites or even in nature, awaiting natural decomposition, uncontrolled incineration, or even being washed toward shores and contributing to marine litter. A substantial portion of these waste streams conceals untapped energy potential. Harnessing the latent energy potential residing within waste materials represents a huge opportunity that can contribute towards the Circular Economy vision of the sector. Such byproducts from waste recovery processes could generate income, supporting sector upgrades with EU Standards and supplying the industry with an alternative fuel directly contributing to the ambitious CO₂ emission reduction. Finally, such practice

addresses other detrimental effects of waste disposal (particularly landfilling and incineration) on the environment and human health. Producing alternative fuels via a waste-to-energy framework can contribute to diversifying the energy mix (especially in industrial processes), reducing overreliance on conventional fossil fuels and fostering energy security. By embracing the potential of 'waste-to-energy', WB countries embark on a transformative journey towards a more sustainable and resilient future, where resourcefulness and environmental responsibility intersect to address some of our most pressing global challenges. This endeavour demands concerted efforts from public authorities and industries to shift from a linear to a circular economy for a low-carbon future.

Key concepts:

Waste-to-Energy	is a broad term identifying the value chain aimed at exploiting the energy potential of waste for heat and/or electricity production.
Circular Economy	a model of production and consumption, which involves sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing and recycling existing materials and products as long as possible.
Refuse-Derived Fuel (RDF)	considered an alternative energy source deriving from the thermal recovery process of domestic and business waste, including biodegradable material, plastics, cardboard, etc.
Solid Recovered Fuel (SRF)	is a high-quality alternative to fossil fuel produced mainly from commercial waste, wood, textiles, and plastic. It is widely used in cement kilns to replace fossil fuels. The difference with RDF lies in the refinement level required to meet end-user specifications.

Alternative fuels - the international practice

Refuse-Derived Fuel (RDF) and Solid Recovered Fuel (SRF), deriving from defined waste streams, have emerged as promising energy alternatives for power generation since the 1990s. The primary objective of this practice is to reduce the amount of waste that ends up in landfills or gets incinerated and prevent inadequate waste management practices while reaping the economic benefits embedded in waste (waste as a resource). However, as long as waste remains a reality, the most effective approach is to extend the life cycle of resources by repurposing them through reuse and recycling and supporting recovery with energy generation as a last resort.

The relentless march of economic development, population growth and unrestrained

consumption patterns have given rise to an alarming surge in waste production. In addition to the environmental concerns, materials are being dumped even though they embody calorific power that can be reutilised for power generation. Since the mid-90s, several EU countries have embraced technologies for energy recovery from municipal solid waste, making it the current state-of-the-art method. For example, England reduced by 50% the amount of municipal waste landfilled during the last decade and exported about 2.6 million tons of RDF only in 2019. At the same time, replacing fossil fuels with alternative fuels can significantly reduce carbon emissions. For instance, the Austrian-German cement industry replaced fossil-fuels with RDF/SRF by 80% and reduced the sector's carbon emissions by 17%.

Alternative fuels, however, come with a cost, as their chemical composition embeds pollutants such as chlorine, sulphur, and heavy metals. The mixture of pollutants poses risks, which could be more harmful than classic fossil fuels such as coke, lignite, coal, and other derivatives. Risks are exacerbated in countries that have not fully implemented

the 2010/75/EU "Industrial Emissions Directive" (IED). In this context, WB countries must align their national frameworks to EID and the Best Available Techniques (BAT) before fully harnessing the socio-economic and environmental benefits of RDF/SRF co-processing.

Qualitative assessment of production and use of RDF (different years over 2008-2016)

Source of data: Trends in the use of solid recovered fuels - IEA Bioenergy

Status Quo in the Western Balkans

Municipal waste management is a real challenge in the Western Balkan (WB) from a regulatory and capacities point of view. WB countries are, arguably, "lost in transition", with large quantities of waste ending up in (un)sanitary landfills and, to a large extent, in informal dump sites. The relatively low cost of landfilling combined with inadequate enforcement of the regulatory framework due to the lack of appropriate human resource capacities and a lack of efforts into structural solutions for waste management poses essential environmental and health

challenges for WB countries. In addition, there is persistent inertia in implementing the waste management hierarchy¹, where disposal should be the last option for waste treatment. The short-cut from bin to disposal and a *not-in-my-backyard syndrome* lead to adding pressure from the community and long-term soil, air and water contamination (leakage of lixiviates, toxins and greenhouse gas emissions (GHG)). Meanwhile, finite resources like land are consumed, and valuable materials and energy resources are lost (or locked).

¹as provided by the national legislative framework and in line with the EU Directive 2008/98/EC

A number of societal issues are also of key concern regarding waste management in the WBs, from health impacts to the working conditions and livelihood of those working with waste sorting. In Albania alone, it is estimated that between 355 and 500 Romani and Egyptian families were actively engaged in informal waste segregation of glass, metal, plastic, and paper during 2012-2018. These communities' livelihoods depended on this informal activity. Recycling companies benefited significantly from it until the waste management service was re-organised by most of the municipalities, and they were cut out (without any option for integration and provision of the service formally). Since then, the recycling rate in Albania has declined from 18% to 5%.

WB countries have made substantial commitments to curtail their GHG emissions by 2030 and promote a sustainable future for their citizens and the planet. Albania, in particular, has vowed to reduce its emissions by an impressive 20.9% compared to the business-as-usual scenario by the end of 2030. North Macedonia has set a highly ambitious target, pledging to decrease its greenhouse gas emissions by a staggering 82% by 2030 compared to 1990. Meanwhile, Serbia has also made a notable commitment, aiming to reduce its emissions by 33.3% by 2030 compared to 1990. These commitments strongly signal these countries' intentions to tackle the climate crisis and achieve their goals. Yet, intentions need to be translated into actions.

The potential of alternative fuels in the WB

The existing issues of waste management in the WBs and commitments to curtailing GHG emissions are compelling reasons to seek and explore sustainable waste recovery strategies. These strategies not only divert non-recycled waste from landfills but also convert it into a valuable energy resource, giving value to the waste and expanding the range of fuels available for thermal industrial processes beyond what's achievable through incineration's heat recovery. Concurrently, a dynamic shift is underway in the industrial sector towards the energy-from-waste approach, particularly emphasising its

implementation in the cement industry. Related businesses in WB have voiced their inclination to replace a significant portion, up to 25%, of their current fossil fuel usage with alternative sources such as RDF/SRF. This transition is primarily motivated by cost efficiency (savings in operating costs from fossil fuels) and the imperative to curb GHG emissions. The latter contributes to mitigating industries' carbon footprint and transitioning into more sustainable production processes.

Data shows that over the last five years, large quantities of waste were disposed of,

Soruce: www.stat.gov.rs

Soruce: www.monstat.org

Soruce: www.instat.gov.al

averaging about 91% in Serbia, 67% in North Macedonia, and 67% in Albania (see Figure 2). To assess the potential of the energy-to-waste approach, a thorough [market research and feasibility study](#) were carried out in 2021 across WB countries, including Albania's North region, Serbia's Duboko region, and

North Macedonia's Skopje region in 2021. Findings suggest that adopting the energy from the waste approach could reduce landfilled waste by ~11-17%, add to the existing supply of alternative fuels by ~37,154 tons per year, and reduce CO₂ emissions by about 37,154 tons annually.

Recommendations

The commitments made with the Paris Agreement on climate change, New Urban Agenda, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 11, 12) represent a major challenge requiring a collective effort from decision-makers, businesses, and society. Yet, changing the mindset from waste to resource – and using the economic potential of waste can bring huge opportunities for improving the quality of the service, generating jobs, creating ground for adequate integration of marginalized groups, improving public hygiene as well as directly contributing to social awareness about consumerism and sustainability.

We provide a list of recommendations with some hints on enabling this process in the best possible way.

- **Develop expertise and capabilities in the public and private sectors to design and adopt alternative business models with public-private-community participation (shared benefits business models).** In this approach, communities are well-informed, engaged, and committed to sharing the costs and benefits of any adopted solution. Engaging local communities (residents and businesses) in shared benefits business models can change their behaviors to waste management policies and practices, facilitating a gradual shift from disposal-oriented (linear) to value-creation (circular) approaches.
- **Channel funds on waste management and treatment infrastructure** to increase service standards, territorial coverage, and segregation in order to increase recycling, reusing and recovery.
- **Introduce RDF/SFR production as an alternative that might generate twofold benefits for local communities.** On the one side, the environmental benefits of reducing quantities of waste stocked in landfills and/or incinerated progress towards a circular economy. On the other side, the economic benefits related to economically viable business models, new jobs created locally and potential alleviation of poverty for disadvantaged societal groups (such as the Roma community).
- **Ensure compliance with internationally recognized standards for effective waste recovery and co-processing of RDF/SRF producers and users.** In this direction, aligning the national to the EU regulatory framework presents an opportunity for WBs to access international markets for alternative fuels.
- **Strongly coordinate efforts in waste management with local authorities,** from strategic planning to updates to the regulatory framework. Then, proceed to introduce, adapt, and implement waste management plans and practices on a practical level, involving local communities and private actors.
- **Implement the waste management hierarchy effectively to advance sustainable waste management practices.** Both public and private stakeholders must take coordinated actions that prioritize waste reduction at its source, promote reuse and recycling, and increase maximum recovery capacities.
- **Raise awareness and increase transparency by engaging communities on waste management issues.** An essential ingredient for the success of waste management initiatives is the dissemination of information, transparency in processes, and the fostering of public engagement and awareness (on negative and positive aspects). These initiatives gain invaluable momentum by ensuring that citizens are well-informed and can actively participate in decision-making processes.

ABOUT THIS POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief was developed by GreenFORCE, a Horizon Europe project which aims at fostering excellence in the “Western Balkans’ green transition” and scientific research capacities of Co-PLAN, Institute for Habitat Development (Albania), Center for Economic Analysis (North Macedonia), and University of Belgrade, Faculty of Geography (Serbia). In twinship with Nordregio - Nordic Institute for Regional Development and Planning - (Sweden) and Politecnico di Torino (Italy), these organisations work closely to produce territorial knowledge through exploratory research and institutional learning.

The policy brief and recommendations build on previous research conducted by Co-PLAN on [Waste to Energy in the Cement Industry for the Western Balkans](#) and further discussion amongst researchers from the GreenFORCE consortium partnership.

Funded by
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Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Graphics by Merita Toska and Klesta Galanxhi

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